

ELIXIR Community Database (ECD)

Checklist Version 1 - July, 2025

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ELIXIR Community Database Checklist

Purpose

This document is a lightweight checklist to assess the suitability of an ELIXIR Service Delivery Plan (SDP) resource to be selected by an ELIXIR Community for [ELIXIR Community Database \(ECD\)](#) status. It is hoped to identify high quality biodata resources serving ELIXIR Community scientific niches that may never be within scope of ELIXIR Core Data Resource (CDR) or ELIXIR Deposition Database (EDD) status. The checklist will ultimately help ELIXIR Communities receiving an ECD status application determine:

- If a resource is of a minimum quality to be awarded an ECD status.
- If a resource would benefit further from ELIXIR Community engagement to support their development roadmap and advance their service quality based on Community user needs.
- Identify gaps & opportunities:
 - Best practices and international standards adoption to support interoperability.
 - Reduce database silos and ensure ECD biodata resources can federate data into the existing biodata ecosystem of resources (within and beyond ELIXIR).

Checklist completion information

All fields must be completed by the ECD applicant and the application submitted in PDF format to: elixir-community-databases@elixir-europe.org.

Note - checklist feedback: This checklist is designed for the pilot ECD programme, it will be adapted and refined in further versions based on the ECD pilot feedback participants. All feedback can be submitted alongside the application to: elixir-community-databases@elixir-europe.org

Note - text length: Keep text short and succinct, please do not give too much text.

Note - reapplications: Are only possible after 12 months and all failing feedback must be addressed in bullets in Appendix 1 (Only for resubmissions).

Sections

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Applicant details

Submitter(s) name	First Last (indicate lead)
Submitter(s) email	Email (institutional only)
ELIXIR Node(s)	ELIXIR-XX
ELIXIR Institute(s)	Name
Resource name	Name
Resource weblink	URL
Resource software repo (e.g. GitHub)	URL
ELIXIR Community submitted to	To choose ▾
Date submitted	day-month-year

Section 1: Eligibility check

Please read the following eligibility requirements before completing this application. For any questions or uncertainties please contact: elixir-community-databases@elixir-europe.org.

1. The primary applicant is a member of an ELIXIR Node & Node institute ([check here](#)).
2. The applicant is submitting an ELIXIR Node Service as listed on the ELIXIR SDP ([check here](#)).

3. The service being submitted contains biological data and is one of the following:
 - a. A deposition database (public store of biodata)
 - b. A curated knowledgebase (curated biodata information extracted from literature)
 - c. A biodata registry
 - d. An aggregation database

4. The service does not already hold a status of:
 - a. [Core Data Resource \(CDR\)](#)
 - b. [ELIXIR Deposition Database \(EDD\)](#)
 - c. [Global Core Biodata Resource \(GCBR\)](#)
 - d. [Recommended Interoperability Resource \(RIR\)](#)

5. For federated and consortia databases (multi-site, multi-branding, non-ELIXIR Involvement), please contact the support email to determine eligibility.

I confirm that my biodata resource is eligible under the above criteria:

Section 2: Resource Background

1. **Biodata resource key info:**
 - a. Gap your resource serves:
 - i. [100 words - keep short]
 - b. Biological data type(s) held & total entries:
 - i. Biodata type (number of entries)
 - ii. ...
 - c. Uniqueness:
 - i.
 - ii. List overlapping resources serving the same gap
 - iii. State what your resource does better than resources serving the same gap
[100 words - keep short]
 - d. Relevance to designated ELIXIR Community:
 - i.
 - ii. [100 words - keep short]
 - e. Peer-reviewed article on your database itself (e.g. NAR Database/+)
 - i.
 - ii. **If yes:** provide link

2. **How long ago did your resource officially go live?**
 - a.

3. **Has your resource been part of:**
 - a. A funded ELIXIR Community Commission Service work plan?

- i.
 - ii. **If yes:** provide short description/link [100 words - keep short]
 - b. A funded ELIXIR CMR/BFSP/HDTR Science Tier Commission Service work plan?
 - i.
 - ii. **If yes:** provide short description/link [100 words - keep short]
 - c. An ELIXIR BioHackathon project /AHM workshop/ other?
 - i.
 - ii. **If yes:** provide short description/link [100 words - keep short]
4. Is your resource a niche biodata resource of use by a narrower life science subdomain e.g. aligned under one of the ELIXIR Community focus areas?
 - a.
5. Do you believe there is scope for your resource to eventually mature into a CDR/EDD scale resource (e.g. ENA/UniProt/+)?
 - a.
6. Have you already applied for CDR/EDD status?
 - a.

Section 3: User base monitoring

1. Do you have resource monitoring in place? e.g. for uptime & response time metrics.
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description [100 words - keep short]
2. Are you tracking any quantitative resource usage data metrics? e.g. monthly users/+
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description [100 words - keep short]
(do not provide any metrics)
3. Have you considered the possible user base growth of your target domain community?
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description [150 words - keep short], e.g.
 - i. Active user growth trends
 - ii. Conference sizes
 - iii. Publications & possible ingestible data
 - iv. Other...

Section 4: Development, Staff & Governance

1. **Do you have a resource update strategy or development roadmap?**
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description [100 words - keep short]

2. **Does your resource collect user base feedback and community input for its development roadmap?**
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description [100 words - keep short]

3. **Does your resource have a helpdesk?**
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description [100 words - keep short]

4. **Does your resource have details publicly available about who works on your resource?**
 - a. [100 words - keep short]

5. **How many people (approximate in FTE) work on your resource?**
 - a. [100 words - keep short]

6. **Is the resource operated across more than one institution?**
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description [100 words - keep short]

7. **Does your resource have dedicated funding to:**
 - a. Retain staff to curate data, maintain & update it?
 - i.
 - ii. **If yes:** provide short description (institutional support/in-kind support/grants/+) [100 words - keep short]
 - b. Provide dedicated hardware to keep it live & online (at least for next 2 years)?
 - i.
 - ii. **If yes:** provide short description [100 words - keep short]

8. **Do you know how many of your team members would have to leave the project for the resource to stop further development/new data ingestion?**
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description [100 words - keep short]

9. Does your resource have a scientific advisory board (SAB)?
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description/link [100 words - keep short]

10. Does your resource have a privacy statement?
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description/link [100 words - keep short]

11. Does your resource have an ethics policy? (e.g. for sensitive data)
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description/link [100 words - keep short]

Section 5: Interoperability, Standards & Data flow

1. Does your resource use metadata standards for its data?
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description/link(s) (FAIRsharing standard link if available) [100 words - keep short]

2. Does your resource use an ontology for its data?
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description/link(s) (Ontology Lookup Service link if available) [100 words - keep short]

3. Does your resource expose structured data (e.g. JSON/W₃C/DCAT)?
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description/link(s) [100 words - keep short]

4. Does your resource provide an API/FTP/other protocols for exposing and retrieving the data in a machine actionable manner?
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short list

5. Does your resource pull data from other data resources? (inflow of data)
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short list

6. Do other resources pull data from your resource? (outflow of data)
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short list

7. Have you identified/roadmapped existing (ELIXIR) biodata resources that could augment their database entries by pulling in your data?
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short list & information [100 words - keep short]

Section 6: Data & Software Management

Data

1. Do you have a publicly available data management plan?
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description/link [100 words - keep short]

2. What is the license for use of the data in your resource?
 - a. Provide short description [100 words - keep short]

3. Do you have a clear plan for long-term storage and off-site backups?
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description/link [100 words - keep short]

4. Do you maintain version archives of the database contents?
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description [100 words - keep short]

Software

5. Do you have a publicly available software management plan?
 - a.
 - b. **If yes:** provide short description/link [100 words - keep short]

6. What is the license for use of the software of your resource?
 - a. Provide short description [100 words - keep short]

7. Is your data resource's software available in containerised format for reuse?
(eg: Docker image/Podman/Singularity)
 - a.

b. **If yes:** provide short description/link [100 words - keep short]

8. **Is your data resource's software open source? (i.e. the code base is reusable and available to redeploy?)**

a.

b. **If yes:** provide short description/link [100 words - keep short]

Section 7: Use of ELIXIR Biodatabase Supports

1. **Is your resource listed in a database registry such as FAIRsharing?**

a.

b. **If yes:** provide link

2. **Does your resource have its identifiers registered in identifiers.org?**

a.

b. **If yes:** provide link

3. **Are any analysis tools & workflows provided by your resource registered in relevant registries such as bio.tools and WorkflowHub?**

a.

b. **If yes:** provide link

4. **Are any training materials for your resource registered in TeSS?**

a.

b. **If yes:** provide link

5. **If reliant on data curation does your resource use APICURON for curator credit and recognition?**

a.

b. **If yes:** provide link

6. **If reliant on a user authentication and authorisation infrastructure (AAI) service, do you use LS-AAI?**

a.

7. **Do you use any resource monitoring supports such as OpenEBench's observatory?**

- a.
- b. **If yes:** provide link

8. Please provide a screenshot from the [FAIRchecker](#) result for your resource:

a.

9. Are you aware of and developing your resource in alignment with RDMkit guidance?

a.

10. Are you aware of and developing your resource in alignment with RSQkit guidance?

a.

Section 8: Final Declaration

By submitting this application form, I that:

1. Our resource is subject to a one year health check period following a successful ECD application.
2. We agree to actively engage with the ELIXIR Community accrediting our ECD to identify and address achievable checklist gaps where development resources allow.

Appendix 1: ECD Reapplication

If this is a resubmission after the 12 month feedback period has passed since the formal ECD Rejection by a Community after an initial failed application, please state under each section in succinct bullets what has been done to address the original feedback.

Note: to be considered for reapplication this section **must be completed** in detail.

Section 1: Eligibility check

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Section 2: Resource Background

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Section 3: User base monitoring

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Section 4: Development, Staff & Governance

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Section 5: Interoperability, Standards & Data flow

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Section 6: Data & Software Management

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Section 7: Use of ELIXIR Biodatabase Supports

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